

DC-XA ENGINE PLUME DIAGNOSTICS: DATA COLLECTION UTILIZING A COTS PC

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ABSTRACT

Marshall Space Flight Center's Optical Plume Anomaly Detection (OPAD) systems have been developed for the purpose of monitoring rocket engine health by identifying and quantifying trace elements in exhaust plumes. The opportunity to put an OPAD instrument aboard the DC-XA test vehicle afforded a valuable first chance to test the technology in an environment for which it is ultimately intended. Methods used to accomplish this are discussed herein, with a focus on the miniaturized personal computer used for data collection. Also, a brief examination is made of test results.

BACKGROUND

For several years, Marshall Space Flight Center (MSFC) personnel have been collaborating with other NASA centers, governmental agencies, universities, and businesses in attempts to apply spectrometric analysis to the monitoring and diagnosis of rocket engine health. The Space Shuttle Main Engine Technology Test Bed in Marshall's West Test Area has been home during this time to several incarnations of optical sensor systems designed to identify trace metals in exhaust. At MSFC, instruments for this purpose are classified as Optical Plume Anomaly Detection (OPAD) systems.

While advances were being made in OPAD technology, the question was being asked: "Will it fly?" For this reason, the opportunity to put a test instrument aboard the Delta Clipper Experimental Advanced (DC-XA) test vehicle was met enthusiastically. Objectives of this endeavor were to be fairly basic: first, fly a working version of an OPAD instrument; second, use commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) hardware where possible; and third, collect useable data. For NASA, the move toward COTS was an aggressive implementation of recent changes in the agency in attitudes

toward the conventional requirement for much more expensive flight-qualified electronics.

The DC-XA Vehicle

Eventually renamed Clipper Graham, the DC-XA evolved as a much more instrumented and technologically advanced version of the DC-X vehicle. The DC-X was used in eighteen ground tests and eight flights to demonstrate the operational ability of its vertical-takeoff-and-landing design, along with the functionality of required subsystems. With the installation of lighter high-tech fuel tanks, composite structures, several new or advanced supporting systems, and additional instrumentation including an OPAD system, the DC-XA was born. Ground tests, launches and landings took place at White Sands Missile Range, NM.

Figure 1. DC-XA at Launch

BUILDING THE OPAD SYSTEM

The Control Computer

A decisive first step in producing the DC-XA OPAD involved choosing a hardware platform upon which to build. Although relatively young, the PC/104 format presented a promising miniature computer standard with a rapidly growing vendor base. Restricting individual computer cards to approximately the dimensions of a 3-1/2" floppy diskette, with 0.6" separating cards in a stack, this format provided the potential for a control computer box measuring no more than six inches in any dimension.

No single PC/104 vendor had all of the component cards required to assemble a complete OPAD control system. For this reason, the Central Processing Unit (CPU) card, and Analog-to-Digital Converter (A/D) card were purchased from Real Time Devices, while a Flash Disk card came from M-Systems, an Enhanced Serial Communications Card (ESCC) from WinSystems, and a DC-to-DC power supply from Tri-M. The ESCC was already rated for extended temperature range operation (about -40 to +80 C), while the remaining boards were screened for this capability at an extra charge. Additionally, a standard temperature range video card was purchased from RTD for use during system development.

The CPU, model CMi486SLC-2, was based on a 33-megahertz 80486 processor, and came with 4 megabytes of RAM. The board also included external floppy disk interfacing, one parallel port, and two programmable serial ports, among other options. One of the two serial ports was used for an on-ground communication link through a vehicle umbilical. Since this connection was broken on liftoff, the port had to be disabled at engine start to prevent spurious interrupts from open leads. The interim physical link traversed approximately four miles between the launch and control sites via optical fibers.

Configuration of the computer for various operational modes was accomplished through the serial ground link. By writing new versions of the `autoexec.bat` file into the root directory, the system could be set for flight, calibration, data transfer, or diagnostic activities as needed.

RTD's DM408-2 A/D card was used to convert analog pixel levels from the spectrometer assembly to digital counts, at twelve bits of resolution. Set to accept an input voltage range of zero to ten volts, this board could sustain conversions at a rate of 200,000 per second, with higher rates possible in burst mode. In addition, because the card

had the capability to generate interrupts based on multiple digital inputs, it was also used to detect status signals from the DC-XA flight control computer for test start and shutoff. Storage of executables and data files was accomplished on M-Systems' PC/104-FD-16-V flash disk card. This card had the capability to carry 32 Mbytes of solid-state memory, but study revealed that 16 Mbytes would be more than sufficient. During development of system software, it was discovered that the flash disk required delivery of data in one-megabyte portions to prevent onset of a period of downtime about every fifteen seconds for housekeeping. As a result, it became undesirable to use the disk for storage of flight data. Instead, the disk was used primarily for data storage during calibrations.

Figure 2. Control Computer Assembly

While the capacity for on-board data storage existed and was exploited, experiment plans called for, and vehicle design provided a means for sending data to ground computers during flight. The alternative was to download test data through the RS-232 ground link post-flight, which required about an hour just to transfer calibration files. Instead, high-speed multiplexer and radio frequency equipment developed by Gulton Data Systems (now Goodrich Aerospace) accepted the data stream from the OPAD control computer and transmitted it to the ground. With 12 bits of resolution per pixel, 1100 pixels per spectrometer array, and four arrays sampling twice per second, the data rate amounted to only 13,200 bytes throughput per second, plus some overhead bytes. A serial clock rate of 264 kHz was more than sufficient to move the data, and the Gulton system was not even remotely challenged by the load.

Because the serial ports on the CPU could not operate faster than 56 kbps, a separate high-speed serial port was required

to communicate with the telemetry system. The WinSystems PCM-ESCC-16 filled this requirement nicely. This highly configurable two-channel card was able to accommodate three twisted, shielded pair RS-422 lines: two received clock and sync signals from telemetry, while the third transmitted synchronous data in return.

The power supply, from Tri-M of Canada, topped the stack. It operated on an input range from about eight to over thirty volts DC, delivering +/-5V and +/-12VDC through the PC/104 bus. One of the primary reasons for the choice of this particular supply was that it seemed to be the only one available at the time capable of sufficient -12V output for operation of the A/D card. On the other hand, a major obstacle was encountered in the use of this supply: it was discovered that by default bus control signals were terminated on the card in such a way as to interfere with operation of the computer. Upon removal of the offending components, the PC/104 stack performed as expected.

Power supply efficiency was about 85%, so its heat sink got quite warm during operation; for this reason, it was necessary to install the stack in the enclosure upside down, with the heat sink resting on a thermally conductive pad on the computer's mounting plate. This scheme worked very well, wicking excess heat to the avionics rack. Before the DC-XA flew, Tri-M introduced a new supply with well over 90% efficiency and lower operating temperatures, but it was decided that the original unit would suffice.

Temperature concerns were present because the vehicle would stand in the desert sun for days, then be tanked with cryogenic fuels for the last few hours prior to launch. The avionics rack was known to reach over 120°F under some conditions, but prior to testing no hard data existed on how cold the rack should get with fuel loaded. It turned out that while temperatures in such locations as the intertank area approached cryogenic temperatures during flight, the avionics rack apparently remained much more tolerable.

Additional concerns stemmed from limited information on the levels of vibration to be expected. For this reason, the computer cards were modified somewhat: on-board jumpers were soldered in place; all signals out of the enclosure passed through soldered connections; wire bundles and socketed chips were tied down with lacing cord; the clock battery was sandwiched between cards using RTV silicone; and plastic spacers, insulators and standoffs were replaced with stainless, teflon and mica. All of the flight cards were stacked with stainless standoffs and installed in a custom enclosure from parvus Corporation. Cost of the computer cards was approximately \$4K, and the custom enclosure was another \$1K.

Software was developed in Borland C++ on a separate desktop computer, then ported to the control computer using LapLink. For several reasons, including RAM and flash disk space limitations, the compiled executable was targeted to the DOS environment. Modifications of the executable at the launch site, and downloading of certain data files, were accomplished through the CPU serial port; unfortunately, this link was limited to a rate of 9600 baud, a relative snail's pace. Originally planned as a single twisted, shielded pair half-duplex RS-485 communication link, the final configuration reverted to RS-232 (two signal leads and a ground) because no commercially available communication software and hardware combinations were found capable of true half-duplex operation.

Spectrometers

Spectrometer units were housed apart from the control computer. Ocean Optics provided four miniature spectrometers, each different from the standard COTS unit only in that its lens assembly was mounted in epoxy for stability. The four units were stacked using stainless steel standoffs and mounted in a custom enclosure produced in-house at MSFC. As with the control computer assembly, additional measures were taken to harden the spectrometer stack for the expected flight environment: signal connections were made by soldered wire, and discrete components were secured with lacing or RTV. Cost of the assembly was approximately \$4K. Its largest dimension was six inches.

Figure 3. Spectrometer Assembly

Light from the engine plumes at the base of the vehicle had to be collected and presented to the spectrometers in the

avionics rack near the top of the vehicle. For this purpose, each unit had a 400-micron UV-grade quartz optical fiber which ran 17 meters from a miniature telescope assembly near its assigned engine nozzle to the spectrometer. Fibers were purchased from Ocean Optics for about \$400 each. Arnold Engineering Development Center designed and produced the telescopes in-house.

Figure 4. Telescope Assembly with Fiber

System Assembly and Integration

System integration and checkout were anything but straightforward. Because of a short project timeline, the variety of sources contributing hardware, and the informal manner by which it was acquired, all major components of the DC-XA OPAD met for the first time upon installation into the vehicle at the McDonnell-Douglas facility near Huntington Beach, CA. Besides the fact that most of the hardware was then forty feet off the ground and only accessible from lifts, access was severely limited by the many other activities taking place during final assembly of the vehicle.

Despite harried and somewhat inhospitable conditions, and the lack of assembly instructions in many cases, the system was successfully installed and checked out. Each telescope was assembled and secured in place in an engine “eyeball” – the sliding-seal protective bottom closure surrounding a nozzle. Optics were aligned to view each engine plume exclusively, looking outward and downward at a point in the plume centerline approximately 17” from the nozzle. Since the eyeball moved with the engine nozzle, this orientation remained fixed. The optical fibers were taped in place down the sides of the fuel tanks, then run along the ductwork and wiring harnesses to the bottom of the vehicle, where a short

length of free-hanging fiber spanned the last few inches to the telescopes. The fibers’ mini-SMA connectors were secured with RTV to keep vibration from rattling them loose, and the seams on the spectrometer box were covered with aluminum tape. Finally, the ground communication link was tested and basic operation of the system confirmed.

FLIGHT TESTING

Calibration and Pre-Test Activities

Before each test of an OPAD system, a series of calibrations must be performed to ensure that test data subsequently collected is meaningful. Such a series includes scans of the optical field as it is exposed in turn to ambient light, a calibrated wavelength source, and then a calibrated intensity source. Ambient light data is subtracted from the other data sets to help negate the effects of background light conditions and electronic “dark current” noise. Wavelength data allows correlation of individual data points to specific wavelengths. Finally, intensity calibration helps to correlate an intensity count for a given data point to the actual optical intensity emitted by the engine plume at the corresponding wavelength.

Long before the DC-XA was shipped to White Sands, it was obvious that calibrations on-site would not be simple. The process itself is unwieldy: a large tripod, heavy power supply, and miscellaneous calibration lamps are required. Just getting a power cord to the equipment was a challenging prospect. Placement of the fixtures would be complicated by an uneven terrain, and there was no assurance that sufficient clearance existed near the telescopes for acceptable positioning.

Because of hectic activity expected just before tests, and the fact that hazardous fuels would be present, access for calibrations could not be scheduled on test days. Instead, it was agreed that these procedures would take place one day ahead, at approximately the same time of day expected for the test. Even so, other pad activities often eclipsed calibration time; although one hour was scheduled, on some occasions this was cut at the last moment to thirty minutes or less. Weather conditions were often to blame. Many days, sand storms came up with little warning, whipping blinding white walls of sand into the area with winds up to 50 mph. Spectacular lightning storms were not unusual. One would thus be exceptionally misguided in referring to operations under the vehicle as “relaxed.”

Cryogenics presented an additional problem for calibration. Because fuel was not present during calibrations, but was present during tests, temperature conditions obviously varied from one case to the other. The extent to which this difference affected the quality of calibrations was never fully quantified, but may have been substantial. On the other hand, these effects should have been mitigated by the thermal mass of the avionics rack, the heat generated by the electronics there, the enclosures shielding the hardware, and the normally short test duration. And because the option of calibrating with cryogenics present was out of the question, this issue was somewhat moot.

Just prior to commencement of the test series, it was discovered that some mishandling of the fiber cables had resulted in breakage of two of the four fibers installed on the vehicle. Replacement fibers were quickly obtained and installed on-site without major impacts to system viability. However, it was apparent that regardless of the purported hardness of the cable design, and what pains had been taken to instruct technicians in appropriate handling procedures, early fears about fiber fragility were justified. While the mishandling in this case was egregious, the relatively gentle handling of replacements did not prevent breakage of a different pair of fibers later. For reasons discussed below, it was never possible to fully investigate the latter breakage.

In several cases, the vehicle stood uncovered on the pad for a week or more between test attempts. In addition, it was not unusual for access to be denied for two or more days following a test. Personnel would thus return to the site a few days prior to the next test and find that repairs were necessary. On two occasions, OPAD telescope windows were found shattered in their assemblies, requiring rapid removal, repair and reinstallation. In the summer, the rainy season having set in, the base of the vehicle once collected a few inches of standing water before it was discovered and drained. And, of course, white gypsum dust was found regularly in some very unusual places.

Static Engine Firing

Static firings preceding the first flight of the DC-XA afforded the first real opportunities to solidify procedures and verify the system. While data were collected before and during these firings, various problems prevented successful collection of both valid calibrations and test data during any given test. On the other hand, the fact that the electronics operated at all under such extreme conditions was very encouraging.

One important discovery during this time was that the solar spectrum reflecting off of the white sand was practically drowning out light from the calibration lamps. While this phenomenon had never been encountered so dramatically under conditions of previous testing, it was not insurmountable. The procedures were modified – spectrometer integration time was increased during calibrations – and test participation took place uninterrupted.

Flight

Following static testing, the OPAD system continued to operate through all four flights. However, telemetry downlink failure during the first flight prevented collection of any flight data whatsoever. Then, the system did not receive its startup signal from the vehicle computer on flight two. Data was successfully collected during the third flight, but the pre-flight calibration was found to be invalid. Finally, the fourth flight yielded success. Engine ignition and shutdown were detected in this data, as evidenced by spectral activity; figure 5 shows emission activity at engine start plus three seconds.

Figure 5. Engine 2 Emission Spectrum at T+3 sec.

These results were especially exciting considering earlier speculation that metals could not be detected in DC-XA plumes. Personnel familiar with the operation of the RL10 engines had indicated before testing began that the exhaust might not be hot enough to excite optical energies from trace metals, should any find their way into the plumes. Nevertheless, it appears that the explosive energy of ignition

combined with the erosive nature of startup conditions prevailed, providing success for the OPAD.

Flight four was unexpectedly the last flight of the DC-XA. The vehicle failed to deploy one of four legs while landing, and so fell over, exploded and burned. Amazingly, the OPAD boxes were not consumed by the initial fireballs or the subsequent few hours of exposure to the burning vehicle. In some cases, all that remained of boxes less than a foot away was the lower inch or so of their enclosures.

Upon removal from its blackened enclosure, the control computer appeared untouched by its experience. It is in fact still operational, except for the serial ground communication link. RTD suggested that the wiring into the serial port may have carried enough concentrated heat directly into the interface chip to damage it while leaving the remaining electronics unharmed. Further investigation into this failure has not yet taken place.

Figure 6. Control Computer after the Fire

The spectrometers, housed in a much lighter and poorly sealed enclosure, did not appear to fare as well though located mere inches from the control computer. The optical fibers were burned away to nubs protruding only an inch or so from the enclosure, the metal of which was obviously distorted by heat. Wiring and boards were coated with thick black soot and the covers over the optical components appeared charred. Nevertheless, when sufficient bravery was mustered to plug in the assembly, no obvious malfunctions could be detected.

While it is hardly conceivable that the optics were completely unaffected, all four units collected reasonable

data when exposed to calibration sources, and appeared to be fully functional.

Figure 7. Spectrometers after the Fire

LESSONS LEARNED

Technically, all of the basic objectives of this project were met. An OPAD system built with COTS hardware was flown to altitudes of several thousand feet, and valid data were collected. Even though only one set of data from one engine for one flight was the immediate final product, a wealth of information was gleaned to benefit future incarnations of OPAD.

The exercise itself emphatically pointed out the necessity for rethinking aspects of ground-based OPAD hardware in order to adapt and harden it for vehicle environments. Calibration procedures must be reworked to make them faster and more compatible with launch operations. The use of cryogenics in proximity to the OPAD instruments presents its own set of complications. And problems experienced with serial ground communication indicate that remote computing, as it relates to the requirements of this type of endeavor, is a very young technology.

One approach to solving problems with fragile optical fibers is the use of armored fibers. This option is becoming more readily available and less expensive, for a larger variety of types and sizes of fibers. Also, there is the obvious solution of running fibers inside conduit. The chief problem with conduit is what kept it off of DC-XA: it must be planned into the design from the start. Not only must accommodation be made in the vehicle plumbing, but there must also be a means for integrating the conduit into fixtures

at both ends, so that the fibers are protected at these two most critical points.

New calibration techniques are being pursued. Integrating spheres with intensity calibration lamps and power supplies self-contained are under consideration. Positioning such an apparatus should be much less critical and time consuming, and should yield better results.

Already, newer COTS hardware is being released onto the market. Better, faster and smaller computers came out even before the DC-XA flew. Firmware and software development is becoming more supportive of remote access to embedded systems. More recently, new and vastly improved spectrometers have been purchased and put to work at MSFC. NASA is now preparing to install a system based upon the DC-XA OPAD on the Space Shuttle.

As OPAD technology advances, efforts are turning toward the possibility of near-real-time analysis and diagnosis of engine health. High-speed dedicated computers are being tuned to the complicated task of autonomously identifying metallics and other species in spectral data. Envisioned for the long term is the computational expertise to quantify erosion, decide its significance, and communicate with vehicle control systems when information requires action. Whatever the future holds, the DC-XA OPAD was one big step in the right direction.

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